

The rule of Emotional Intelligence in the process of change management.

Auteur 1 : GHALMI Meriem.

Auteur 2 : BEKKAOUI Abdelmalek.

Meriem GHALMI (Doctorante)

Doctorante au laboratoire Universitaire de Recherche en Instrumentation et Gestion des Organisations (LURIGOR)

Faculté des Sciences Juridiques Économiques et Sociales
Université Mohammed Premier Oujda- Maroc

Abdelmalek BEKKAOUI (Enseignant-Chercheur,PES)

Professeur d'enseignement supérieur

Faculté des Sciences Juridiques Économiques et Sociales
Université Mohammed Premier Oujda- Maroc

Déclaration de divulgation : L'auteur n'a pas connaissance de quelconque financement qui pourrait affecter l'objectivité de cette étude.

Conflit d'intérêts : L'auteur ne signale aucun conflit d'intérêts.

Pour citer cet article : GHALMI .M & BEKKAOUI ,A (2024). « The rule of Emotional Intelligence in the process of change management », African Scientific Journal « Volume 03, Numéro 27 » pp: 0473 – 0483.

Date de soumission : Novembre 2024

Date de publication : Décembre 2024

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.14469833

Copyright © 2024 – ASJ

Abstract

In an era of organizational change imposed by technological advances, the role of the manager has become twofold. They are required to both embrace this change by supporting the transformation of roles, rethinking new modes of leadership and organization, and also to make their employees accept this change.

In this context of change, the organization needs to establish a learning culture that is conditioned by positive emotions. Hence, the importance of emotional intelligence, which facilitates this organizational transition and enables the entire hierarchy to adapt to the transformation while striving to find a balance and potentially benefit from it.

This work aims to analyze how the emotional intelligence can explain and contribute to the change dynamic.

To analyze this relationship, we have developed experimental design by comparing two groups through longitudinal approach and quantitative methodology.

After analyzing data and evidences we have clearly found that emotional intelligence can predict the performance of leaders and managers in the change situation.

Key words: emotional intelligence, leadership, organizations.

Résumé

Dans une ère marquée par des changements organisationnels imposés par les avancées technologiques, le rôle du manager est devenu double. D'une part, il doit adopter ces transformations en soutenant la reconfiguration des rôles, en repensant les nouveaux modes de leadership et d'organisation. D'autre part, il doit également accompagner ses employés dans l'acceptation de ces changements. Dans ce contexte, l'organisation doit établir une culture d'apprentissage conditionnée par des émotions positives. D'où l'importance de l'intelligence émotionnelle, qui facilite la transition organisationnelle, permettant à l'ensemble de la hiérarchie de s'adapter aux transformations, tout en recherchant un équilibre et des opportunités de valorisation.

Ce travail vise à analyser comment l'intelligence émotionnelle peut expliquer et contribuer à la dynamique du changement. Pour examiner cette relation, nous avons élaboré un protocole expérimental comparant deux groupes à travers une approche longitudinale et une méthodologie quantitative. L'analyse des données et des preuves recueillies révèle clairement que l'intelligence émotionnelle peut prédire la performance des leaders et des managers dans des situations de changement.

Mots clés : Intelligence émotionnelle, Leadership, organisations.

Introduction

Today, the world is undergoing profound changes, whether in terms of the balance of global powers, the structure of economies, or shifting alliances and detachments. Economies have been significantly impacted by the pandemic and its aftermath, as well as by the ongoing effects of the war between Russia and Ukraine. These disruptions have profoundly affected global trade and value chains. Additionally, new policies aimed at addressing climate change are influencing the global economy. Morocco is no exception, as its institutions, businesses, and individuals must navigate a constant cycle of short and unpredictable changes. In this context, organizations and their leaders are compelled to adapt to the reality of perpetual transformation. The relationship between leaders and their teams during such times has been the subject of numerous theories, which seek to explain this dynamic and identify optimal strategies as well as the necessary skills to drive meaningful impact.

Previous research suggests that emotional intelligence (EI) can significantly enhance leadership effectiveness, particularly in times of change. Studies indicate that EI competencies such as empathy, self-regulation, and motivation play a crucial role in fostering an environment conducive to positive change.

This research investigates the impact of leaders' EI on organizational performance through a longitudinal study conducted over six months. Two groups were analyzed: a test group, consisting of managers with high levels of EI, and a control group, composed of managers with lower EI scores. By combining real-world observations with assessment tools like the Goleman EI test, this study seeks to provide concrete evidence of the relationship between emotional intelligence and effectiveness in change management.

This paper is structured as follows: the first section, **Research Design**, outlines the general framework of the study and its theoretical foundations. The second section, **Methodology**, details the stages of the research, including the longitudinal approach, research protocol, case studies, instruments employed, data collection, and analysis methods. The third section presents and discusses the results, highlighting the key implications of the study. Finally, the conclusion synthesizes the main contributions and proposes avenues for future research.

1. Research design

“One obvious reason to use experimental design is its ability to provide evidence of causality (Philip & Nathan, 2018)

Indeed, as the quote at the beginning of this article points out, the power of experiments in establishing causal relationships is essential for the development of knowledge in organizational science and behavior.

It is not surprising, therefore, that Jones (1985, p. 282) argues that the experiment is "the most effective technique available to demonstrate causal relationships between variables", and researchers Others Philip et Nathan, 2018 have called them the "gold standard" of scientific research”.

The aim of using this technique of research is to increase the quality of results that can be verified. For this purpose, we have chosen a methodology and research protocol that can help us to achieve our objective.

2. Methodology

In our work we aim to analyze the relationship between leadership emotional intelligence and change management through specific sears that take time as a variable in account. To respond to these purposes, we have chosen a Company that is in a period of several internal changes in terms of process and external changes in terms of stakeholders and governance.

Our methodology is quantitative based on the character of data and type analysis which is based on Likert scale and statistical analysis. (Ulrika, Lisa, Yvonne, & Neneh, 2011)

2.1. Longitudinal research

To assess effectively our problem and ensure the quality of results and discussion we have chosen to observe the evolution of results through time by using some performance indicators from the internal KPI's through the period of 6 months.

Longitudinal studies are most interesting in terms of explaining the phenomenon by taking in account the effect of time which allow to observe the dynamic of the model and generate more insightful ideas about the topic. (Elisabetta, 2000)

2.2. Protocol of research

To operationalize our work, we have assessed after agreement with the direction about the confidentiality and ethical elements in our research.

Our research has taken into account team Managers and divided it into two groups for tests and two for control of the results.

The protocol of research consists firstly on identifying the high ranked profile in the company on Emotional Intelligence Test and the lowest ranked one after this step our work consist of observing results for a period of 6 months started from 15/01/2023 to 15/07/2023 which is the planned periods for implementing new tools of work and restructuring information and communication system.

After this period, we have distributed a survey to the employees that work with each manager to assess their feedback about their managers and change process.

2.3. Case study

The used case study was pertinent and reliable in terms of companies that we have chosen from others and which live those last five years in permanent changes. (Petri & Julie, 2019) One of the biggest challenges that face this company is to do process reengineering and to reorganize all companies.

The external forces that are driving these changes are the privatization, the change of the governance entity, the entry of new players and the customer quality that should increase to survive. For the internal forces the high charges of salary, the complexity of the old process and the time to market issues.

The company works in the logistics sector and runs the operations of containers and the activity of import and export which is a strategic activity for our economy.

2.4. Research instrument

The instrument of research that we have used is the Goleman Test which its first purpose is to analyze the leader profile in change situations and which is assessed to ensure its validity and reliability. (Wolff, 2005)

“Emotional intelligence skills appear to work more effectively in synergistic groups, with evidence suggesting that mastering a critical mass or skill set is a necessary barrier to awakening skills. in other groups, but when both are shown, the person is often more effective at work and career. management positions.” (Mohammed, 2018)

“The first cluster of emotional competencies within the personal competences domain is Self-Awareness. Self-Awareness is characterized by a deep understanding of one’s emotions, strengths, and weaknesses, and the ability to accurately and honestly self-assess.

Fundamental concepts of Self-Awareness include individuals’ personality traits, personal values, emotions, habits and the psychological needs that drive behaviors. Three competencies lie within the Self-Awareness cluster: emotional self-awareness, self-assessment, and self-confidence.” (Mohammed, 2018)

“Emotional self-awareness reflects the importance of recognizing one's emotions and how they affect one's performance. Recognizing one's own strengths and weaknesses is an attribute of self-assessment.

The third skill in the Self-Awareness cluster is confidence. The ability to make the right decisions despite uncertainty and pressure, the ability to voice unpopular views, and the ability to be assertive are all characteristics of confident people.

Self-management involves one's ability to control and regulate one's emotions, the ability to stay calm, lucid, and focused when things don't go according to plan, as well as the ability to self-motivate and take the initiative. The Self-Management Emotional Intelligence Competency Cluster is the second cluster in the Personal Competences area and includes six competencies: autonomy, dependability, conscientiousness, adaptability, will to succeed, and initiative. Self-control is the ability to deal with one's own distressing and distressing emotions and impulses by controlling them (BOYATZIS, 1982).”

“Credibility means making others aware of one's values and principles, intentions and feelings and acting consistently with them (CHERNISS; GOLEMAN, 2001).

Adaptable people are flexible in the way they view events, can handle multiple requests with ease, and can adapt their reactions and tactics to flexible situations active.

Social cognitive skills determine how to relate to others, especially the ability to sense other people's emotions and read the moods of a group; inspire and build relationships; working in conditions; listen and communicate. Being sensitive to others is crucial to outstanding professional performance, whenever the focus is on interacting with people.

Three skills are found in the Social Cognitive cluster of the Social Competence domain: empathy, service orientation, and organizational awareness. Empathy is the ability to feel the feelings and perspectives of others and take an active interest in their concerns. Service-oriented competencies are concerned with anticipating, recognizing and responding to customer needs.” (Cary & Daniel, 2003)

“The third competence in the Social Awareness cluster is organizational awareness. Individuals with this ability can understand the political forces at work in an organization, as well as the guiding values and unspoken rules that operate among the people.

Relationship Management, the second cluster in the Social Competence domain, has to do with a person's ability to manage relationships with others and involves the ability to communicate, influence, collaborate, and work with colleagues. (Cary & Daniel, 2003)

The Relationship Management cluster focuses on essential social skills and includes the following competencies: developing others, influence, communication, conflict management, leadership, change catalyst, building bonds, teamwork and collaboration.

Developing others entails sensing what others need in order to develop and reinforce their abilities. A leader who has mastered the influence competence uses complex strategies like indirect influence and persuasion to build harmony and support with others.

Those excelling in the leadership competence are able to articulate and arouse enthusiasm for a shared vision and mission, to step forward as needed, to guide the performance of others while holding them accountable, and to lead by example. (Cary & Daniel, 2003)

Those proficient as change catalysts are able to challenge the status quo, to acknowledge the need for change. Leaders must also be able to recognize the need for change, remove barriers, and enlist others in pursuit of new initiatives. The cornerstone of the building bonds competence is networking and nurturing instrumental relationships, all of which are essential for successful change.”

All those elements are used in our research as a survey for assessing the leader characteristics and observe the evolution through time:

2.5.Data Gathering

The gathering of data was based on two approaches: the first one is about the survey designated to the managers and to their teams and the second one about the using of internal data like the KPI's to ensure the quality of our results.

Our first step was based on finding leaders with different capabilities and teams with comparable capabilities based on their performance to analyze the situation which was so difficult because we haven't found a perfect starting point but a comparable case which we will present in the results.

The test group aims to assess the impact of managers that have a high Emotional intelligence cluster and score and compare it with the group of control that have a moderate or low score to observe the results through time.

To control the other variables, we have identified that the groups benefit from the same advantages and have access to the same resources and are comparable in terms of diploma which is technical training for all participants.

The decomposition of groups is constituted by one manager and five operators for each group that work on Casablanca port.

2.6.Data Analysis

Our data analysis process was based on the protocol of interpretation identified through the technical document of Goleman Survey, 2001 and about the analysis time series data simply by using the curve of evolution and the regression test.

3. Results and Discussion

To present and discuss our results we aim to separate the results of the test group from the results of the group of control to give the lecture the possibility to analyze and interpret the results. But before we need to present the starting point to assess the changes by using some types of internal indicators.

Table 1: Table of comparison between the groups

Parameters	Starting points		Final Assessment	
	Group of test	Group of control	Group of test	Group of control
Agility of services	85%	80%	95%	87%
the mean Performance of collaborators	97%	94%	112%	98%
Mean of Adoption of the new tools	-	-	2,5 months	4 months

Source: Compiled by the author.

From the table before we can clearly identify the Gap that has been developed between the two groups and the high performance of the group of tests that is distinguished by the high score of emotional intelligence of their leaders.

The results verify the assumptions of the law of minimal improvement which, represented by the equation of 1 with the power of 365 days of years, is equivalent to 37 which is the output of little bit of difference.

To assess more of those results we have chosen to present the indicators in the curve to observe the evolution more precisely:

Figure 1 : Group of test

Source: Compiled by the author.

from the graph before we can observe a significant evolution that reaches its peak point in the third month with high performance. the explanation cannot be just related to leadership attribute but also to the learning curve of the team which is a contingency factor that can explain the dynamic of the change.

Figure 1 : Group of control

Source: Compiled by the author.

After discussing the results and the evolution of performance we should be presenting and discussing the results of the team perception which will prepare us to explore the model of leaders that perform the process of change:

Table 2: Team Test Results

	Self (Personal Competence)	Test	Control	Other (Social Competence)	Test	Control
Recognition	Self-Awareness			Social Awareness		
	• Emotional self- awareness	4.7	3.2	• Empathy	4.4	4
	• Accurate self- assessment	4.3	3.5	Service orientation	4.5	3.6
	• Self-confidence	4.6	3.1	• Organization awareness	4.2	4.1
Regulation	Self management			Relationship management		
	• Self-control	3.9	3.8	• Development others	5	3.9
	• Trustworthiness	4.4	3.7	• Influence	4.5	3.4
	• Conscientiousness	4.6	3.7	• Communication	4.8	3.2
	• Adaptability	5	3.5	• Conflict management	4.3	4.1
	• Achievement drive	4.6	3.3	• Leadership	4.5	4.2
	• Initiative	5	3.7	• Change catalyst	4.6	4
				• Building bonds	4.6	3.8
			• Teamwork & collaboration	4.7	4.1	

Source: Compiled by the author.

The results shown before explain the performance discussed before in the first and second tables. The results show that there is some kind of equilibrium between personal competence and social competence.

Those results show also that leaders who had achieved high results on emotional intelligence tests have a high score on the level of relationship management which explain the difference in performance results and change dynamics.

Conclusion

In this work we have analyzed the relationship between emotional intelligence and change management through a scientific procedure that can be reliable and scientifically valid. The experimental design of research and longitudinal observation was the most appropriate methodology that matched our research objective.

We can clearly define that emotional intelligence plays a significant role in explaining the dynamics of change which basically take the actors as the principal determinants of change dynamics.

In our work and through the evidence that we had gathered, we have well defined the link between emotional intelligence and change management. Our work has contributed to professional development of the organization.

After discussing results with managers responsible for career development, they took the tools seriously and showed the intention of adopting the survey for the promotion of middle managers.

Bibliography

Cary, C., & Daniel, G. (2003). *The Emotionally Intelligent Workplace: How to Select For, Measure, and Improve Emotional Intelligence in Individuals, Groups, and Organizations*. John Wiley & Sons.

Edward Joseph Caruana, 1. M.-S. (2015). Longitudinal studies. *journal of thoracic disease*.

Elisabetta, R. (2000). Longitudinal Research in the Social Sciences. *University of Surrey*.

Mohammed, I. (2018). Change Leadership: The Role of Emotional Intelligence. *Sage Journal*.

Petri, Y., & Julie, Z. (2019). Case study research in the social sciences. *Elsevier*.

Philip, P., & Nathan, P. (2018). Experimental designs in management and leadership research: Strengths, limitations, and recommendations for improving publishability. *The Leadership Quarterly*.

Ulrika, Ö., Lisa, K., Yvonne, W., & Neneh, R.-D. (2011). Combining qualitative and quantitative research within mixed method research designs: A methodological review. *Elseviers*.

Wolff, S. (2005). *Emotional Competence Inventory (ECI) Technical Manual*. Hay Group, McClelland Center for Research and Innovation.